

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FACTOR INFLUENCE ASSESSMENT ON THE EFFICIENCY AND INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UKRAINE

Myroslav Sukhar,

Researcher of the Department of Scientific Support for Innovative Development of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences

Oleksandr Khmil

postgraduate student of the National Scientific Center "Institute of Agrarian Economics"

Abstract

The target of the study was to measure the dependence of the net profit of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine on the current dynamics of agricultural production, the number of people employed in the agricultural sector of the economy, the negative dynamics of the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture. An appropriate correlation-regression model of the dependence of the net profit of agricultural enterprises on the current dynamics of selected factors was developed.

Keywords: net profit, investment activity, employment, agrarian entrepreneurship, factor influence.

The foundation of Ukraine's food, economic and national security has been and remains the agrarian sector of the economy, which synergistically combines the existing natural resource potential and entrepreneurial activity of agricultural enterprises. Over the past 30 years, Ukraine has gradually strengthened its production potential and steadily increased the export capabilities of its agricultural sector. During 2010-2021. The domestic agricultural sector has gained significant development momentum over the past 10 years - agricultural production increased by 52.4% - from 467.5 to 712.6 billion UAH, and the share of agricultural exports during this period increased from 19.3 to 40.7%.

The war had a catastrophic impact on the functioning of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine.

The influence of internal and external environmental factors on the functioning of agricultural enterprises was studied by L. Rohatyna [1], R. Sodoma, T. Shmatkovska [2] and many other researchers. M. Nегrey, O. Trofimtseva [3] thoroughly investigated the problems of the functioning of the agricultural sector of Ukraine in wartime and justified the need for its support both from the state and from foreign funds, organizations and states.

D. Kopta and J. Lososová [4], A. Bezat-Jarzębowska and W. Rembisz [5] and V. J. Martinho and D. Pereira [6] analyzed the reasons for changes in the profitability of agricultural enterprises and the impact of some financial indicators (the ratio of current assets to total assets, the ratio of current liabilities to total assets and the ratio of debt to total assets) on profitability. Ł. Kryszak et al. [7] and F. Günther et al. [8] showed that an increase in the subsidy rate leads to a higher profitability of assets of medium-sized enterprises and the growth of households.

Taking into account the works of scientists considered above, we emphasize that under the new economic conditions, the paradigm of effective management has changed dramatically. Therefore, it is advisable to consider efficiency not simply as a ratio of results and costs, but also as the degree of use of the production and economic potential of an economic object.

The purpose of the article is to model the dependence of the dynamics of net profit of agricultural enterprises of Ukraine on the current dynamics of agricultural production, the number of employees in the agricultural sector of the economy, the dynamics of the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture.

Materials and methods

The functional dependence of the net profit of agricultural enterprises on the selected independent influencing factors can be described as follows:

$$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) \quad (1)$$

Determining the objective presence and influence of uncertain random factors that are of a force majeure nature and cannot be measured by specific indicators, we note that the selected random variable Y (net profit) will fluctuate from a functional dependence. In this case, the dependence will not be functional, but stochastic in nature and will have the following mathematical interpretation:

$$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) + \beta \quad (2)$$

where β is the random deviation

Further practical implementation of the methodological tools of correlation-regression modeling of the dependence of net profit on the dynamics of agricultural production, the number of employees in the agricultural sector of the economy, the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture is based on the assumption of a linear relationship between Y and X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 :

$$Y_{\text{mpi}} = a_0 + a_1 x_{\text{Prodi}} + a_2 x_{\text{Wi}} + a_3 x_{\text{Eni}} + a_4 x_{\text{Ini}} + \beta_i \quad (3)$$

where $a_0, a_1, a_2, b_0, b_1, b_2$ are the parameters of the regression equations;

Y_{mpi} is the dynamics of net profit of agricultural enterprises in the i-period, billion UAH,

x_{Prodi} is the dynamics of agricultural production in the I period, billion UAH,

x_{Wi} is the dynamics of the number of employed workers in agriculture, thousand people,

x_{Eni} is the number of agricultural enterprises in the i -period, thousand units

x_{Ini} is the dynamics of investment volumes in agriculture in the i period, billion UAH,

β_i is the random deviation that interprets the cumulative impact of unaccounted factors and contingencies

Results and discussion

Military operations have caused a significant reduction in the areas available for harvesting, and a large

part of agricultural land has fallen beyond the physical limits of its cultivation. Almost 2 million hectares remain mined.

Over the 2 years of the war, the number of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine has decreased by 11.1% or by 7,141 units. The number of workers employed in agriculture has decreased by 105,100 people - from 511,100 to 406,000 (Table 1)

Table 1

Dynamics of indicators of the state of agricultural entrepreneurship in Ukraine, billion UAH

Indicator	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2023 in % to 2021
Revenue from sales of products	467,6	525,1	556,3	605,5	918,7	680,5	780,0	84,9
Production costs	399	481,5	508,6	512,3	606,2	599,7	694,5	114,6
Financial result before tax profit	68,6	71,5	94,0	82,2	240,0	87,3	65,4	27,3
loss	88,7	94,4	116,6	108,6	248,3	126,4	99,4	40,0
Percentage of profitable enterprises	20,4	22,9	22,5	26,4	8,3	39,1	34,1	410,8
Investments	86,7	86,3	83,1	82,7	88,3	78,5	78,4	-9,9
Number of agricultural enterprises, thousand units	57,8	65,9	55,3	36,4	49,1	32,6	31,6	64,4
Number of employed, thousand people	76,6	76,3	75,5	73,4	70,8	53,3	63,0	89,0
	593	549,3	537,2	510	511,1	433,4	406,0	79,4

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [9]

Accordingly, the decrease in the number of enterprises and employed workers allowed the corresponding relative indicators of agricultural production to remain at the level of previous periods. Thus, the production of agricultural products per 1 enterprise decreased by only 5.4% (from 10,970 to 10,355 thousand UAH), and per 1 employed person increased by 5.7% (from 1,394 to 1,473 thousand UAH). The net profit of agricultural enterprises of Ukraine during the war decreased by 2.5 times - from 248.3 to 99.4 billion UAH. At the same time, the loss incurred by agricultural enterprises increased by 4 times - from 8.3 to 34.1 billion

UAH.

As for the volume of capital investments, the absolute indicator of investment investments decreased by 35.6% - from 49.1 to 31.6 billion UAH.

A retrospective analysis of the performance indicators of agricultural enterprises allows us to conclude that the highest levels of profitability were achieved in the pre-war 2021 (Table 2). Thus, the profitability of agricultural operations reached 39.4%, borrowed capital – 43.6%, equity – 30.0%, current assets – 27.2%, sales – 26.0%.

Table 2

Dynamics of performance indicators of agricultural enterprises of Ukraine, 2017-2023

Indicator	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2023 in % to 2021
Return on non-current assets	37,1	30,6	32,2	26,3	69,4	25,5	17,4	-52
Return on current assets	10,7	10,9	14,6	11,5	27,2	8,8	6,2	-21
Return on capital	7,5	7,2	9,1	7,2	17,8	6,0	4,1	-13,7
Return on equity	15,7	14,7	17,8	13,3	30,0	10,6	7,2	-22,8
Return on debt	14,4	14,2	18,4	15,8	43,6	13,6	9,7	-33,9
Return on operating activities	17,1	14,7	18,3	15,9	39,4	14,4	9,1	-30,3
Return on sales	14,6	13,5	16,8	13,5	26,0	12,7	8,1	-17,9
Labor productivity, UAH million per employee	1,11	1,22	1,27	1,20	1,39	1,24	1,47	105,8

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [9]

During the war, the profitability of agricultural operations decreased almost threefold - from 39.4 to 9.1%. The efficiency of using agricultural enterprises' own capital decreased by 4 times, borrowed capital - almost 3 times, current assets - 5 times. Sales profitability fell by 4 times - from 26.0 to 8.1%.

The use of correlation analysis tools for selected time periods established the following relationships.

Thus, the pair wise correlation coefficients are equal to:

the dependent variable Y (net profit of agricultural enterprises) with independent X_1 (agricultural production, billion UAH), X_2 (number of employees in the agricultural sector of the economy, thousand people), X_3 (number of agricultural enterprises) and X_4 (volume of investments in agriculture, billion UAH) $R_{px1} = 0.57$, $R_{px2} = 0.53$, $R_{px3} = 0.62$ and $R_{px4} = 0.64$, respectively, and between the independent factors themselves there is a closer relationship: $R_{x1x2} = 0.54$, $R_{x1x3} = 0.56$, $R_{x1x4} = 0.69$, $R_{x2x3} = 0.78$, $R_{x2x4} = 0.77$, $R_{x3x4} = 0.45$ (Table 3).

Comparison of correlation matrices by production and net profit of agricultural enterprises

Net profit of agricultural enterprises				
Y	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄
1				
0,570255	1			
0,530463	0,542049	1		
0,624415	0,564455	0,783798	1	
0,647664	0,694065	0,768245	0,447833	1

Source: authors' calculations

In other words, there is a relationship between the dynamics of net profit of agricultural enterprises and negative trends in the reduction of production, the number of agricultural enterprises, employed workers and the reduction of investment activity in agriculture.

The results of applying the regression analysis tool to assess the impact of the negative dynamics of the reduction of agricultural production, the number of employees in the agricultural sector of the economy, the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture on the net profit of agricultural enterprises are summarized in Table 5.

The processing of the corresponding dynamic series of actual indicators of net profit, production, the number of agricultural enterprises, employed workers

and the volume of investments for the period 2015-2023 allowed us to determine the following parametric values of the coefficients of multiple correlation and determination - 0.929 and 0.863, respectively. We cannot but state the presence of a stronger relationship between the net profit of agricultural enterprises and the set of selected influencing factors.

Resulting parameters of the correlation-regression analysis of the impact of agricultural production, the number of employees in the agricultural sector of the economy, the dynamics of the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture on the net profit of agricultural enterprises for the period 2015-2023.

Table 5

Equation	Multiple correlation coefficient R	Determination coefficient R ²	Fisher's coefficient F-criterion	Student's t-test
Net profit of enterprises				
$Y = -708,368 + 1,638388X_1 + 1,191115X_2 - 7,80485X_3 - 6,02528X_4$	0,929	0,863	Actual 6,305 Tabular 3,633	tx ₁ =5,015 tx ₂ =2,442 tx ₃ =-2,980 tx ₄ =-3,412

Source: authors' calculations

The determined coefficients of multiple determination indicate that the net profit of agricultural enterprises depends on the existing dynamics of production, the number of employees, the number of enterprises and investment activity in the agricultural sector by 86.3%.

Accordingly, the remaining 13.7% of the variable profit values were determined by the factor influence, which is not covered by the area of our research.

The calculated value of the F - criterion (6.305) with a probability of 0.95 exceeds the specified tabular parameter, which states the reliability of the constructed model. The corresponding check of the significance of the coefficients of multiple correlation using the parametric tool of the Student's t-criterion proved that for all four factors of influence with a probability of 0.95, the threshold parameter $t_{0.95(9)} = 2.262$ is exceeded. This once again states the significant significance of the influence of the selected factors.

Formalized correlation-regression models of the dependence of net profit on the current dynamics of agricultural production, the number of employees, the dynamics of the number of enterprises and the volume of investments in agriculture have the following form:

$$Y = -708,368 + 1,638388X_1 + 1,191115X_2 - 7,80485X_3 - 6,02528X_4$$

where Y is the theoretical value of the indicator of net profit of agricultural enterprises, billion UAH,

X₁ is the dynamics of agricultural production, billion UAH,

X₂ is the dynamics of the number of employees, thousand people,

X₃ is the dynamics of the number of agricultural enterprises, thousand units,

X₄ is the dynamics of investments in agriculture, billion UAH.

The established correlation-regression dependencies allow us to interpret the nature of the change in the net profit of agricultural enterprises from the existing dynamics of the selected influencing factors as follows:

an increase in the volume of agricultural production by 1 billion UAH leads to an increase in net profit by 1.64 billion UAH;

an increase in the number of employees by 1 thousand people increases net profit by 1.19 billion UAH per year;

a decrease in the number of enterprises by 1 thousand units reduces the net profit of agriculture by 7.8 billion UAH;

a decrease in investments in the agricultural sector of the economy by 1 billion UAH reduces the net profit of agriculture by 6.03 billion UAH.

Conclusions.

The war has had a catastrophic impact on the health, well-being, incomes and living conditions of Ukrainians. The country's economy continues to suffer catastrophic destruction and losses. However, the Ukrainian agricultural sector has withstood and is adapting to the difficult conditions of wartime. After all, providing the population and the army with food is an extremely priority and important task.

Ukraine remains one of the main guarantors of global food security. During 2022-2023, the share of sunflower oil production in global production is 27.8%, barley - 4.0%, wheat - 2.7%, corn - 2.0%, sugar - 0.8%.

The military conflict caused the closure of a significant number of enterprises: the number of large enterprises decreased by 20% in agriculture and 15% in the food industry, medium-sized ones - by 20% and 11%, small ones - by 32% and 27%. The share of profitable enterprises in agriculture decreased from 88.3 to 78.4%.

In the conditions of a full-scale war, the agricultural sector of Ukraine continues to maintain its production and export potential, and after victory it will become the driver of the post-war recovery of our country. However, the problem of lack of financial and investment resources remains extremely relevant. Currently, the key direction for state economic policy is to provide agricultural producers with financial resources by providing targeted assistance - grants and loans.

References

1. Rogatina L.P. Assessment of the impact of macroenvironmental factors on the development of agricultural enterprises. Investments: practice and experience. 2018, 3, 79-85.

2. Sodoma R., Shmatkovska T., Dziamylych M., Vavdiuk N., Kutsai N., Polishchuk V. Economic efficiency of the land resource management by agricultural producers in the system of their non-current assets analysis: a case study of the agricultural sector of Ukraine. Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development. 2021, 21(2), 577-588. <https://sci.ldubgd.edu.ua/jspui/handle/123456789/8536>

3. Negrei M. V., Trofimtseva O. V. Analysis of the functioning of the agricultural sector of Ukraine in the conditions of war. Bulletin of Kharkiv National University named after V. N. Karazin, series "Economic". 2022, (102), 49-56. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2311-2379-2022-102-06>

4. Kopta D., & Lososová J. The development of the profitability of agricultural enterprises and its causes. Inproforum. 2023; 17(1): 243-248. doi: 10.32725/978-80-7694-053-6.36

5. Bezat-Jarzębowska A., Rembisz W. Changes in purchase prices and efficiency vs. production profitability in agriculture: Analytical and empirical approach. Problems of Agricultural Economics. 2022; 372(3): 5-20. <https://doi.org/10.30858/zer/153031>

6. Martinho V. J., Pereira D. Profitability and financial performance of European Union farms: An analysis at both regional and national levels. Open Agriculture. 2022; 7(1): 529-540. DOI: 10.1515/opag-2022-0108

7. Kryszak Ł., Guth M., Czyżewski B. Determinants of farm profitability in the EU regions. Does farm size matter? Agricultural Economics. – Czech. 2021; 67(3): 90-100. doi:10.17221/415/2020-AGRICECON.

8. Fink Günther, B. Kelsey Jack, & Felix Masiye. Seasonal liquidity, rural labor markets, and agricultural production. American Economic Review. 2020; 110(11): 3351-92. DOI: 10.1257/aer.20180607

9. Official website of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine. (2025). Available at: <http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua> (Accessed March 22 2025).